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Ultra-stable cryogenic international temperature comparator with microkelvin instability

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Abstract

After the redefinition of the kelvin in 2019, several start-of-the-art primary gas thermometry techniques were successfully implemented at low-temperature regions. To further make a direct and reliable international comparison of thermodynamic temperature T , we have developed an ultra-stable cryogenic international temperature comparator (CITC) working from 4 K to 25 K. Based on our design and developed temperature control methods, ultra-high stable temperature was achieved with stabilities (standard deviation) better than 10 μK from 4 K to 25 K. The long-term temperature instability is 6.1 $\mu\text{K}@4$ K, 6.7 $\mu\text{K}@5$ K, 7.8 $\mu\text{K}@13.8$ K and 7.4 $\mu\text{K}@24.6$ K with a sampling time of 33.6 s. Moreover, multibridge, especially four-bridges, comparison and calibration methods were proposed to realize temperature measurements in a more precise and efficient way. The feasibility was demonstrated by using one AC bridge and three super-thermometers. The performance of CITC and the proposed methods in this work showed their great superiority to be used for temperature comparison and calibration.

Keywords: international temperature comparator, international comparison, calibration, thermodynamic temperature, primary gas thermometry, temperature instability, thermometer

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1. Introduction

In 2019, the basic unit of thermodynamic temperature, kelvin (symbol K), was redefined by fundamental constant, namely the Boltzmann constant. Compared with the previous definition of kelvin, $1/273.16$ of the temperature of the triple point of water (exactly 273.16 K) [1], the redefined one has more distinct advantages in long-term instability and global universality. This opens a new door for implementing and disseminating the kelvin more precisely at ultra-low temperatures and ultra-high temperatures [2]. To date, several state-of-the-art primary gas thermometry techniques were successfully implemented at low temperatures. These include acoustic gas thermometry (AGT) [3–5], dielectric constant gas thermometry (DCGT) [6] and refractive-index gas thermometry (RIGT) [7–12], as summarized in figure 1. These advances enable direct dissemination of thermodynamic temperature traceable to the redefined kelvin. The feasibility has been demonstrated in single-pressure RIGT (SPRIGT) from 5 K to 25 K by building a wire scale of thermodynamic temperature, denoted $T_{\text{CAS-2025}}$, at Technical Institute of Physics and Chemistry of the Chinese Academy of Sciences (TIPC-CAS) [12].

However, before disseminating the new kelvin worldwide at low temperatures, it is very important to assess the consistency of thermodynamics temperatures (linked to the new kelvin) determined by various primary thermometry. Hence a comparison of thermodynamic temperature T must be performed. Methods for such comparison can be divided into *in-situ* comparison and *non-in-situ* comparison. The former necessitates comparing T , determined by using different primary methods in a single experimental apparatus, whereas the latter does not require such a comparison. Since the former comparison is difficult to carry out, the *non-in-situ* comparison is favored in practice. Usually, *non-in-situ* comparisons include direct comparison and non-direct comparison of T . A non-direct comparisons of T has been carried out by comparing $T - T_{90}$ values from different labs in the world [13], which provides a way to link T_{90} to T by using an analytic function of $T - T_{90}$. Since different labs used different sources of T_{90} , the non-direct comparison cannot satisfy a precise comparison of T linked to the new kelvin. The analytic function is just a compromise solution for those who want to use T in the short term. In the view of long-term development of temperature metrology, it is necessary to make a directly international comparison of T . Now a direct multilateral comparison is currently underway through the DireK-T project (dissemination of the redefined kelvin) [14], with TIPC-CAS as a participating institute.

To carry out a direct T comparison, one should first transfer the measured thermodynamic temperature T to standard resistance thermometers. Then, all thermometers are placed into an ultra-stable measuring environment, where their T data is measured and compared. This process allows for the establishment of international equivalence between different primary thermometry worldwide or can even establish a new International Temperature Scale. It is very complex and difficult to precisely implement a direct T comparison at low temperatures, since every measurement link may introduce an

Figure 1. Measured uncertainties in thermodynamic temperature linked to the new kelvin. Data source: AGT, [3–5]; DCGT, [6]; RIGT, [7–9]; SPRIGT, [10–12].

additional and possibly large uncertainty to that of T . Once this happens, it will influence the accurate evaluation of thermodynamic temperature consistency, therefore reducing confidence and reliability of the comparison.

Besides high-accuracy thermodynamic temperature T (uncertainty $u(T)$ better than 0.3 mK below 25 K [14]), a direct T comparison presents higher requirements for the instability of resistance thermometers (instability better than 0.1 mK, one third of the $u(T)$), which are used to save and reproduce the T data of different labs worldwide. These are (a) robustness of the cryogenic international temperature comparator (CITC) (temperature instability better than 15 μK , one third of the lowest $u(T)$ 50 μK [11, 12]), which is used to provide ultra-stable cryogenic environment for reproducing T , and (b) the reliability of comparison method, which is used to conduct precise measurements. In recent years, to guarantee the reliability of a direct T comparison, meticulous preparation and advanced progress was made on the above key elements at TIPC-CAS: obtaining high-accuracy T with uncertainty better than 0.17 mK [11, 12], developing high-stable platinum-cobalt resistance thermometer (PtCo) with instability better than 0.1 mK [15], designing and constructing an ultra-stable CITC with μK -level instability across 4 K–25 K, and proposing a multibrige measurement method for temperature comparison and calibration.

This work will firstly present the performance of the developed CITC and demonstrate the feasibility of the multibrige comparison and calibration method. It is anticipated that our ongoing research will contribute invaluable input data to the international comparison of thermodynamic temperature for the DireK-T project. Furthermore, we aim to provide the necessary apparatus and methods to facilitate the comparison of T in a wider operating range in the future. This was the aim of the present work. The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 briefly describes the apparatus and experimental methods. Section 3 deals with the results including temperature control and measurement. A conclusion and perspectives in section 4 rounds off the paper.

Figure 2. Cryogenic international temperature comparator (CITC) configuration: (a) cryostat schematic of the cryostat; (b) initial copper block (Runs 1–8), and (c) upgraded microwave resonator configuration (post-Run 8, similar to [16]). The CITC’s copper block and resonator each can accommodate 16 standard resistance thermometers for parallel characterization under identical conditions. The resonator additionally enables *in-situ* thermodynamic temperature measurements via microwave techniques [17–21].

2. Apparatus and methodology

2.1. Cryostat

Figure 2 shows the whole configuration of the cryostat in the CITC experimental apparatus. There are five main cavities inside the cryostat, four of them are made from copper, namely the resonator (electrolytic tough pitch (ETP) copper, ISO norm), the cavities between the structure of the resonator, pressure vessel (oxygen-free high-conductivity), heat switch cavity and the radiation shield. The resonator is the core element used to compare or measure thermodynamic temperature. The main objective of the cryostat is to realize a highly stable temperature control (instability better than 15 μK) of the resonator (or copper block) at 4 K–25 K for temperature comparison (or calibration). To reach this goal, the resonator (or copper block) is first cooled to the target temperature and then actively controlled to achieve the required temperature instability.

Multiple staged components were designed in the cryogenic system to achieve and maintain low temperatures. A commercial pulse tube cryocooler, Sumitomo model SRP-182B2S-F100H cryocooler, was employed to provide the cold source for the system. Its cooling power is 36 W at 48 K for the 1st cold head and 1.5 W at 4.2 K for the 2nd cold head. Besides, oxygen-free copper thermal links were designed and optimized (figure 3 in [22]) to connect the cryocooler’s dual cold heads to the first and second flanges. The thermal links must accommodate two functions, one for enhancing heat transfer and the other for attenuating the temperature fluctuation from the inherent temperature oscillation (typical value 240 mK@3.4 K) of the 2nd cold head of the cryocooler.

To further cooling and reduce the thermal noise from surroundings, three concentric radiation shields were designed

to provide progressive thermal isolation: (1) an outer vacuum Dewar (55 cm diameter \times 102 cm height), (2) an intermediate 50 K shield, and (3) an inner 4 K shield. To further enhance thermal transfer or isolation, a gas type heat switch between the second flange and pressure vessel was designed. It can be activated by introducing helium-4 gas into the interstitial space or closed by pumping out the helium gas continuously with a vacuum pump.

Based on the above designs, the copper block or resonator inside the pressure vessel arrives at the lowest objective temperature of 4 K. With the help of the thermal resistances between the cold heads, thermal links, flanges and pressure vessel, the inherent temperature oscillations of the 2nd cold head could be rapidly attenuated, however it still cannot satisfy the required temperature instability for temperature comparison. So, active temperature control was further developed to better stabilize the temperature of the resonator. This will be introduced in section 2.3.

2.2. Temperature measurement method

All temperature measurements in this study comply with the International Temperature Scale of 1990 (ITS-90) [1], T_{90} , unless otherwise specified. We used two classes of resistance thermometers: positive temperature coefficient (PTC) and negative temperature coefficient (NTC).

2.2.1. Positive temperature coefficient thermometers.

High-accuracy cryogenic measurements of temperature and resistance were performed on the resonator and copper block for calibration and comparison purposes. Two types of PTC thermometers were measured using an AC resistance bridge

Table 1. Resistance bridges and standard resistors information for standard resistance thermometers in this work (unless otherwise specified).

Thermometer label	Resistance bridge	Standard resistor
RIRT_INRiM	WIKA (formerly ASL) F900	WIKA 5685A, 10 Ω , SN 049070-04 (Run 2-Run 9, for temperature measurement)
	WIKA (formerly ASL) F18	WIKA 5685A, 10 Ω , SN 049070-02 (Run 10-Run 18, for temperature control)
RIRT_NIST	WIKA (formerly ASL) F900	WIKA 5685A, 10 Ω , SN 049070-04
PtCo_X1 PtCo_X3 PtCo_X6 PtCo_X9	Super-thermometer 1594A-1	WIKA 5685A, 10 Ω , SN049070-03
PtCo_X2 PtCo_X4 PtCo_X7	Super-thermometer 1594A-2	WIKA 5685A, 10 Ω , SN045068-03
RIRT_NPL3 PtCo_X5 PtCo_X8	Super-thermometer 1594A-3	WIKA 5685A, 10 Ω , SN045068-01

Table 2. Basic calibration information for the RIRTs mounted on the copper block (Runs 2–8) and resonator (Runs 9–18) for temperature measurement (unless otherwise specified).

Thermometer label	Technical parameters	Manufacturers (serial number)	Input format
Copper block (Runs 2–8) and Resonator (Run 9)			
RIRT_INRiM	Calibrated by INRiM, 13.8033 K < T_{90} < 273.16 K	TIPC-CAS and Kunming Dafang Science and Technology Ltd. SN 200920	Equations for $T_{90} = f(R)$ at 0 mA
Resonator (Runs 10–18)			
RIRT_NIST	Calibrated by NIST, 0.65 K < T_{90} < 24.5561 K	TIPC-CAS and Kunming Dafang Science and Technology Ltd. SN 20107	Equations for $T_{90} = f(R)$ at 0 mA
RIRT_NPL3	Calibrated by NPL, NPL-75 with adjustment to ITS-90 for $T_{90} < 24.5561$ K	Tinsley, SN 226950	Equation for $R = f(T_{90})$ at 0.3 mA

and three super-thermometers, referenced to traceable standard resistors (see tables 1 and 2 for specifications).

(1) Standard rhodium–iron resistance thermometer (RIRT)

In this study, three highly stable RIRTs were employed for T_{90} measurements. These included: (1) a 50 Ω RIRT_INRiM (SN 200920, TIPC-CAS/Kunming Dafang Science and Technology Ltd.), calibrated by INRiM (Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica, Italy) to monitor the copper block's temperature instability; (2) a 50 Ω RIRT_NIST (SN 20107, TIPC-CAS/Kunming Dafang Science and Technology Ltd.), calibrated by NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology, USA) as the reference T_{90} thermometer and for resonator instability monitoring; and (3) a 100 Ω RIRT_NPL3 (SN 226950, Tinsley type), calibrated by NPL (UK) for additional resonator instability assessment.

(2) Standard PtCo

We also employed nine high-stability standard PtCos to validate the comparison and calibration method outlined in

section 2.4. These sensors were recently manufactured by TIPC-CAS and Yunnan Dafang Meter Industrial Co. Ltd, and designed with a nominal resistance of $\sim 100 \Omega$ at the triple point of water (273.16 K) to enhance low-temperature sensitivity.

2.2.2. NTC thermometers. In this study, NTC Cernox thermometers were employed to monitor temperatures at both cold heads, two flanges, and the pressure vessel, using Keithley 2002 multimeters. The technical specifications and mounting positions of these sensors are detailed in table 3.

2.3. Temperature control method

2.3.1. Cascade temperature regulation strategy. To achieve highly stable temperature control of the resonator or copper block at low temperatures, a three-level cascade temperature regulation strategy (figure 3) was developed using a hierarchical heating approach. The system consists of three heaters

Table 3. Measurements information for Cernox thermometers used in the CITC system.

Thermometer SN (label)	Model	Technical parameters	Mounting position
XI72547 (TCX1)	CX-1050-CU-HT-1.4L	All calibrated by Lakeshore, $1.4 \text{ K} < T_{90} < 325 \text{ K}$	1st cold head
X172550 (TCX2)			1st pressure tube
X172548 (TCX3)			2nd cold head
X123976 (TCX4)	CX-1050-CD-1.4L		2nd Flange
X172521 (TCX5)	CX-1050-CU-HT-1.4L		2nd pressure tube
X172747 (TCX6)			Pressure vessel flange
X137765 (TCX7)			3rd pressure tube
X172116 (TCX8)			Copper block/resonator

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of three-level cascade temperature regulation scheme.

arranged in a cascaded architecture: (1) the 2nd cold head heater H1 (Q_{Heat1}) at the far end (cold source) provides continuous baseline temperature adjustment, (2) the 2nd flange heater H2 (Q_{Heat2}) mid-system acts as a coarse stabilizer to dampen broader fluctuations, and (3) the pressure vessel heater H3 (Q_{Heat3}) at the proximal end delivers fine-tuned regulation to suppress residual variations. The control process follows a sequential stabilization approach where the cold head temperature (TCX3) is first regulated slightly below the second flange temperature (TCX4), which in turn is maintained just below the target temperature (TCX8) of the copper block or resonator. This hierarchical structure progressively dampens thermal fluctuations, with each stage serving as a thermal buffer for the next. Once TCX4 stabilizes within specified oscillation limits, precise TCX8 control is implemented through optimized feedback parameters, including carefully tuned PID coefficients, ensuring long-term temperature instability with minimal deviation.

2.3.2. Settings of PID control. In this work, precision temperature regulation of both the 2nd flange and resonator was achieved using PID control schemes with dedicated sensing systems: a Cernox thermometer read by a Keithley 2002

multimeter (following methods in [23–26]) for the flange and a RIRT measured with an AC resistance bridge (method in [27]) for the resonator. Detailed information for temperature control is provided in table 4; here we briefly summarize the setup for the copper block and resonator.

Runs 2-9: Temperature control of the copper block (Runs 2–8) and resonator (Run 9) was maintained using a calibrated RIRT (SN LT002, TIPC-CAS/Kunming Dafang Science and Technology Ltd.). The thermometer, calibrated by INRiM (Italy) and denoted RIRT_LT002, was measured using an ASL F18 manual AC resistance bridge with a WIKA 5685A standard 10Ω resistor (SN 049070-02) as reference. Runs 10–18: The resonator temperature was regulated using a calibrated RIRT_INRiM, performed using the same F18 bridge and 10Ω standard resistor.

Temperature resolution is crucial for highly-stable low-temperature control, with three primary determining factors: (1) instrument parameters including bridge voltage noise (presented in this work), excitation current, and integration time (as detailed in [27]); (2) sensor characteristics such as resistance and sensitivity (demonstrated in [12]), along with lead resistances [28]; and (3) standard resistor properties and their associated lead resistances [28].

Table 4. Information of heaters and control thermometers for temperature regulation of both the copper block (Runs 2–8) and resonator (Runs 9–18).

Control components	Technical parameters	Manufacturers (serial number)
Source: Second cold head		
Heater 1	25 Ω	Beijing Hongyu Space Technology co. Ltd.
Thermometer TCX3	Model CX-1050-CU-HT-1.4L Calibrated from 1.4 K to 325 K	Lakeshore, SN X172548
Mid-Path: Second flange		
Heater 2	Model HK6911, 22.08 Ω	Minco Products, Inc.
Thermometer TCX4	Model CX-1050-CU-HT-1.4L Calibrated from 1.4 K to 325 K	Lakeshore, SN X123976
Terminal: Copper block and resonator		
Heater 3	Model 125, 100 Ω	Beijing Hongyu Space Technology co. Ltd.
Copper block (Runs 2–8) and Resonator (Run9)		
Thermometer RIRT_LT002	Calibrated by INRiM, 13.8033 K < T_{90} < 273.16 K, ~50 Ω @ 273.16 K	TIPC-CAS and Kunming Dafang Science and Technology Ltd. SN LT002
Resonator (Runs 10–18)		
Thermometer RIRT_INRiM	Calibrated by INRiM, 13.8033 K < T_{90} < 273.16 K, ~50 Ω @ 273.16 K	TIPC-CAS and Kunming Dafang Science and Technology Ltd. SN 200920

2.3.3. Temperature evaluation index. In this study, the temperature instability is defined as the standard deviation of the measured temperatures ($\sigma(T)$, equation (1)). The average temperature (T_{avg}) and its relative instability ($\sigma_r(T)$) are defined in equations (2) and (3),

$$\sigma(T)/\mu K = 10^6 \cdot \left\{ \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{T_i - T_{\text{avg}}}{1 \text{ K}} \right)^2 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1)$$

$$T_{\text{avg}}/K = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n T_i/K \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_r(T)/\text{ppm} = \frac{\sigma_T/\mu K}{T_{\text{avg}}/K}. \quad (3)$$

2.4. Multibrige comparison and calibration method

2.4.1. Comparison and calibration method. The conventional single-bridge method employs sequential two-current measurements of all thermometers (A–I and reference R). Each measurement cycle follows the pattern ‘ $\hat{R}-\hat{A}-\hat{B}-\hat{C}-\hat{D}-\hat{R}-\hat{E}-\hat{F}-\hat{G}-\hat{H}-\hat{I}-\hat{R}$ ’, where: (1) \hat{R} denotes self-heating measurements of the reference thermometer (currents i_1 , i_2 and i_1 , with i_2 typically $\sqrt{2} \times i_1$); (2) \hat{X} indicates self-heating measurements of thermometer X ; and (3) X represents normal measurements at current i_1 . The reference thermometer measurements at the beginning, middle, and end of each cycle enabled drift correction for the remaining thermometers [29].

We propose a multibrige comparison method, particularly the quadruple-bridge approach, for enhanced temperature measurement precision and efficiency, extending our previous work [10]. As illustrated in figure 4, the method employs sequential self-heating measurements at currents i_1 , i_2 and i_1 (with typical stage durations of $t_0 = 20$ min). The system utilizes: (1) one high-accuracy AC bridge (denoted as Br) paired with a reference thermometer to continuously monitor environmental temperature fluctuations, and (2) three additional AC bridges (B1, B2, B3) that sequentially measure resistances and temperatures in an interleaved pattern ($\hat{B}r \cdot B1 \cdot B2 \cdot B3 \rightarrow Br \cdot \hat{B}1 \cdot B2 \cdot B3 \rightarrow Br \cdot B1 \cdot \hat{B}2 \cdot B3 \rightarrow \dots$). Here \cdot denotes simultaneous measurements by all four bridges, while $\hat{}$ indicates which bridge is performing self-heating measurement at each stage.

This scheme shows that the quadruple-bridge method applies always the self-heating measurement for some thermometer, thereby reducing the thermal disturbance of the unavoidable self-heating changes and improving the measurement efficiency. The quadruple-bridge implementation achieves 2.5 times faster characterization for 12 thermometers across multiple temperature points. This method can be also applied to the initial calibration of thermometers that require self-heating measurements. The multibrige comparison architecture supports customizable redesign based on available instrumentation, where users may adapt the schematic (figure 4) to their specific bridge configurations and preferred self-heating compensation techniques [30], while

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of the proposed multibrIDGE comparison and calibration method. Here we only show the case that the self-heating measured used two currents with equal measurement times.

preserving core parallel measurement and cross-validation by [30, 31] principles.

2.4.2. Self-heating calculation method.

(a) Single-bridge method

For single-bridge method, the zero-current self-heating in resistance R_{SH} and zero-current resistance R_0 can be calculated

R_1 and R_2 are the measured resistance values for the current values i_1 and i_2 , respectively.

By using the law of propagation of uncertainties [32], the corresponding uncertainty for R_{SH} and R_0 are evaluated by:

$$R_{SH} = R_1 - R_0 = \frac{i_1^2}{i_2^2 - i_1^2} \cdot (R_2 - R_1) \quad (4)$$

$$R_0 = R_1 - R_{SH} = \frac{i_2^2 R_1 - i_1^2 R_2}{i_2^2 - i_1^2}. \quad (5)$$

$$u_{R_{SH}} = \frac{i_1^2}{i_2^2 - i_1^2} \sqrt{\frac{4i_2^4}{(i_2^2 - i_1^2)^2} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{u_{i_1}}{i_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_{i_2}}{i_2} \right)^2 \right] \cdot (R_2 - R_1)^2 + (u_{R_1}^2 + u_{R_2}^2)} \quad (6)$$

$$u_{R_0} = \frac{1}{i_2^2 - i_1^2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{4i_1^4 i_2^4}{(i_2^2 - i_1^2)^2} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{u_{i_1}}{i_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_{i_2}}{i_2} \right)^2 \right] \cdot (R_2 - R_1)^2 + i_2^4 u_{R_1}^2 + i_1^4 u_{R_2}^2}. \quad (7)$$

When the sensitivity of thermometers, $S = dR/dT$, the zero-current self-heating in temperature T_{SH} and the zero-current temperature T_0 is given by equation (4)

$$T_{SH} = T_1 - T_0 = \frac{R_1 - R_0}{dR/dT} = \frac{i_1^2}{i_2^2 - i_1^2} \cdot (T_2 - T_1) \quad (8)$$

$$T_0 = T_1 - T_{SH} = \frac{i_2^2 T_1 - i_1^2 T_2}{i_2^2 - i_1^2} \quad (9)$$

$$u_{T_{SH}} = \frac{i_1^2}{i_2^2 - i_1^2} \sqrt{\frac{4i_2^4}{(i_2^2 - i_1^2)^2} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{u_{i_1}}{i_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_{i_2}}{i_2} \right)^2 \right] \cdot (T_2 - T_1)^2 + (u^2_{T_1} + u^2_{T_2})} \quad (10)$$

$$u_{T_0} = \frac{1}{i_2^2 - i_1^2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{4i_1^4 i_2^4}{(i_2^2 - i_1^2)^2} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{u_{i_1}}{i_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_{i_2}}{i_2} \right)^2 \right] \cdot (T_2 - T_1)^2 + i_2^4 u^2_{T_1} + i_1^4 u^2_{T_2}}. \quad (11)$$

(b) MultibrIDGE method

By comparing a reference thermometer with constant current, we can remove the possible drift of the working environment for the compared thermometers by correcting the shift of $T_{mea}(t) - T_{ref}(t)$ in real time, particularly since all thermometers have a similar temperature variation trend with time.

In this way, the self-heating of the zero-current self-heating in resistance R_{SH} and zero-current resistance R_0 in equations (4)–(7) can be calculated by respectively replacing R_0 , R_1 and R_2 to $R_0 - R_{ref,0}$, $R_1 - R_{ref,1}$ and $R_2 - R_{ref,2}$.

$$R_{SH} = (R_1 - R_{ref,1}) - (R_0 - R_{ref,0}) = \frac{i_1^2}{i_2^2 - i_1^2} \cdot [(R_2 - R_{ref,2}) - (R_1 - R_{ref,1})] \quad (12)$$

$$R_0' = R_0 - R_{ref,0} = (R_1 - R_{ref,1}) - R_{SH} = \frac{i_2^2 (R_1 - R_{ref,1}) - i_1^2 (R_2 - R_{ref,2})}{i_2^2 - i_1^2} \quad (13)$$

$$R_0 = R_0' + R_{ref,0} = R_0' + \frac{R_{ref,1} + R_{ref,2}}{2} \quad (14)$$

$$u_{R_{SH}} = \frac{i_1^2}{i_2^2 - i_1^2} \sqrt{\frac{4i_2^4}{(i_2^2 - i_1^2)^2} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{u_{i_1}}{i_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_{i_2}}{i_2} \right)^2 \right] \cdot [(R_2 - R_{ref,2}) - (R_1 - R_{ref,1})]^2 + (u_{R_1} - u_{R_{ref,1}})^2 + (u_{R_2} - u_{R_{ref,2}})^2} \quad (15)$$

$$u_{R_0} = \frac{1}{i_2^2 - i_1^2} \cdot$$

$$\sqrt{\frac{4i_1^4 i_2^4}{(i_2^2 - i_1^2)^2} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{u_{i_1}}{i_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_{i_2}}{i_2} \right)^2 \right] \cdot [(R_2 - R_{ref,2}) - (R_1 - R_{ref,1})]^2 + \left(i_2^2 u_{R_1} - \frac{i_1^2 + i_2^2}{2} u_{R_{ref,1}} \right)^2 + \left(i_1^2 u_{R_2} - \frac{i_1^2 + i_2^2}{2} u_{R_{ref,2}} \right)^2}. \quad (16)$$

Similar to R , the self-heating of the zero-current self-heating in temperature T_{SH} and zero-current temperature T_0 in equations (8)–(11) can be calculated by respectively replacing T_0 , T_1 and T_2 to $T_0 - T_{ref,0}$, $T_1 - T_{ref,1}$ and $T_2 - T_{ref,2}$,

$$T_{SH} = (T_1 - T_{ref,1}) - (T_0 - T_{ref,0}) = \frac{i_1^2}{i_2^2 - i_1^2} \cdot [(T_2 - T_{ref,2}) - (T_1 - T_{ref,1})] \quad (17)$$

$$T_0' = T_0 - T_{ref,0} = (T_1 - T_{ref,1}) - T_{SH} = \frac{i_2^2 (T_1 - T_{ref,1}) - i_1^2 (T_2 - T_{ref,2})}{i_2^2 - i_1^2} \quad (18)$$

$$T_0 = T_0' + T_{ref,0} = T_0' + \frac{T_{ref,1} + T_{ref,2}}{2} \quad (19)$$

$$u_{T_{SH}} = \frac{i_1^2}{i_2^2 - i_1^2} \sqrt{\frac{4i_2^4}{(i_2^2 - i_1^2)^2} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{u_{i_1}}{i_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_{i_2}}{i_2} \right)^2 \right] \cdot [(T_2 - T_{ref,2}) - (T_1 - T_{ref,1})]^2 + (u_{T_1} - u_{T_{ref,1}})^2 + (u_{T_2} - u_{T_{ref,2}})^2} \quad (20)$$

$$u_{T_0} = \frac{1}{i_2^2 - i_1^2} \cdot$$

$$\sqrt{\frac{4i_1^4 i_2^4}{(i_2^2 - i_1^2)^2} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{u_{i_1}}{i_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_{i_2}}{i_2} \right)^2 \right] \cdot [(T_2 - T_{ref,2}) - (T_1 - T_{ref,1})]^2 + \left(i_2^2 u_{T_1} - \frac{i_1^2 + i_2^2}{2} u_{T_{ref,1}} \right)^2 + \left(i_1^2 u_{T_2} - \frac{i_1^2 + i_2^2}{2} u_{T_{ref,2}} \right)^2}. \quad (21)$$

3. Results and discussions

After the CITC was assembled, its performance was optimized to meet the stringent requirements for direct comparison of thermodynamic temperature. The present article deals essentially with cooling performance and temperature regulation behavior of the resonator. Besides, multibridge comparison and calibration method was carried out and its performance was demonstrated.

3.1. Cooling performance

3.1.1. Cooling in different runs. Prior to cooling, the cryostat volumes are evacuated to a base pressure of ~ 1 mPa using a two-stage pumping system composed of turbomolecular pumps (Pfeiffer Vacuum HiPace 700 and 450) backed by scroll pumps (Pfeiffer Vacuum ACP40). Helium gas is subsequently introduced through the heat switch gas line to activate the heat switch.

Figure 5 shows the cooling process monitored over multiple experimental runs during which the heat switch is turned on throughout. The cooling begins at $t = 0$ with the activation of the pulse tube cryocooler. The system reaches its base temperature within 30 h. We note that the cooling rate can be further improved by optimizing the helium gas prefill pressure in the heat switch. In the initial system configurations (Run 1), the copper block stabilized at 4.14 K, failing to meet the target of 4 K. To enhance thermal anchoring, additional thermal links were installed between the second cold head and the flange, reducing minimum the copper block temperature to 3.91 K (Run 2).

In Run 9, the copper block was replaced with a quasi-spherical resonator for future thermodynamic measurements, requiring the integration of coaxial microwave signal lines. These modifications introduced additional heat loads, limiting the resonator's base temperature to 4.02 K, still 20 mK higher than 4 K. In Run 14, the resonator reached 3.94 K by optimizing thermal connections between coaxial cables and the 1st and 2nd flanges, satisfying the < 4 K design specification.

3.1.2. Temperature variation. Temperature instability is a critical requirement for the CITC system. While the pulse tube cryocooler enables continuous operation at 4 K–25 K without liquid helium consumption, its inherent 1.72 Hz temperature oscillations present a significant challenge for precision temperature control and measurements.

Figure 6 quantitatively demonstrates the passive damping of pulse tube-induced temperature oscillations in our system during Run 1 (copper block at base temperature with active heat switch). Synchronized measurements sampled at 0.1 s intervals show the progressive attenuation from the second cold head (243 mK peak-to-peak amplitude at 1.72 Hz) through the thermal isolation stages: the oscillation reduces to 6.5 mK at the second flange and reaches 1.8 mK at the pressure vessel. The corresponding fast Fourier transform (FFT) analysis in figure 7 provides spectral confirmation, showing complete suppression of the 1.72 Hz component in the pressure vessel (residual noise 1.8 mK). This demonstrates

Figure 5. Cooling performance of the cryogenic system with continuous heat switch operation. Run 2: strengthen thermal links between the 2nd cold head and flange. Run 14: strengthen thermal anchoring between coaxial cables and the 1st and 2nd flanges.

Figure 6. Damping of inherent temperature oscillations from the 2nd cold head of the pulse tube in Run 1. Temperatures of the 2nd cold head, 2nd flange, and pressure vessel were respectively measured by TCX3 (SN X172548), TCX4 (SN X12396) and TCX3 (SN 172747) with a sampled time $\tau = 0.1$ s.

the effectiveness of our multi-stage passive thermal isolation design in attenuating pulse tube cryocooler-induced fluctuations by over two orders of magnitude.

However, the residual temperature fluctuations (peak-to-peak 1.8 mK, instability 0.6 mK) significantly exceed the required instability threshold (15 μ K) for precision measurements in our application. To achieve the target instability, active temperature control should be conducted to further improve the temperature stabilization.

3.2. Temperature control performance

Based on the methods and settings in section 2, experimental optimization on measurement device, excitation current, microwave signal power was carried out. A large amount of

Figure 7. Frequency spectra obtained by fast Fourier transform (FFT) for a much denser sample than for the time domain images. The oscillation at 1.72 Hz of the pulse tube is imperceptible at the level of the pressure vessel.

temperature control was performed on the copper block and resonator during different runs of the CITC: (1) copper block ranging from 5 K to 25 K under vacuum in Runs 2–8; (2) Resonator ranging from 4 K to 25 K under vacuum and different pressures in Runs 9–18. After optimization, both the copper block and resonator temperatures were stabilized within the target range with a standard deviation of 10 μK , demonstrating precise thermal control at cryogenic conditions.

3.2.1. Parameters optimization.

(a) Selection of measurement devices

Figure 8 compares temperature measurement performance at 24.5 K (vacuum) using two bridge configurations: a super-thermometer 1594A and an AC bridge F900, with RIRT_NPL3 providing temperature sensing (1 mA excitation, 33.6 s integration). The AC Bridge F900 achieved 2-fold improvement, reducing temperature fluctuations from $\pm 30 \mu\text{K}$ to $\pm 15 \mu\text{K}$ and enhancing instability from 15.1 μK to 6.5 μK . This superior performance results from the F900's lower noise floor and higher resolution compared to the 1594A, particularly when interfaced with the AC F18 control bridge. The average temperatures⁵ show excellent agreement, differing by only 13 μK , well within their combined standard deviation (16 μK). Consequently, the AC bridge F900 was adopted for all resonator temperature measurements in this study.

(b) Excitation current determination

Based on the AC bridge F900 device, we investigated the current-dependent thermal response of the resonator at 5 K by

Figure 8. Temperature measurement performance comparison at 24.5 K (vacuum) between the super-thermometer 1594A (2 s integration, averaged to 34 s) and AC bridge F900 (native 33.6 s integration), both using RIRT_NPL3 with 1 mA excitation. The 34 s average data enable a direct comparison of the two bridges. The 10 Ω standard resistor (WIKA 5685A, SN 049070-02) used for both AC and super-thermometer measurements is traceable to NIM, China, ensuring metrological consistency across all cryogenic resistance calibrations.

varying the excitation current (0.5 mA, 1 mA and $\sqrt{2}$ mA) of the controlled RIRT_INRiM and measured RIRT_NIST thermometers. During these measurements, the PID setpoints remained constant.

Figure 9 illustrates the temperature response characteristics of the resonator under varying excitation currents (0.5– $\sqrt{2}$ mA) at 5 K. Subplots (a)–(c) demonstrate the temperature variations under different measured currents (I_m) while maintaining fixed controlled current (I_c). The differences of average temperature under fixed I_c are not more than 6 μK (figure 9(d)), comparable to their instability. This agreement confirms the validity of the self-heating measurements. While for difference I_c , the differences of average temperature are 0.86 mK between $I_c = 0.5$ mA and 1 mA and 1.15 mK between $I_c = 1$ mA and $\sqrt{2}$ mA. The differences originate from joule heating contribution ($P = I^2R$) of RIRT_INRiM, confirmed by the ratio $1.15/0.86 \approx (\sqrt{2}^2 - 1^2)/(1^2 - 0.5^2)$.

Under a fixed current I_m , the temperature instability improves with increasing controlled current I_c , demonstrating a maximum enhancement factor of 1.8 (figure 9(e)). This improvement primarily results from the enhanced temperature resolution of RIRT_INRiM thermometer, despite the concurrent increase in current-induced self-heating effects. For fixed I_c , optimal instability occurs at $I_m = 1$ mA, representing the balance point between resolution enhancement and self-heating. These findings align with our previous work demonstrating matched temperature characteristics between the controlling and measuring sensors [27]. Based on systematic evaluation of this resolution-heating trade-off, we adopted 1 mA as the standard excitation current for all RIRT and PtCo sensors used in this study (unless otherwise specified).

⁵ All temperature measurements from standard resistance thermometers were corrected to remove self-heating effects in this study.

Figure 9. Current-dependent thermal response of the resonator at 5 K. (a) Temperature comparison under controlled excitation current $I_c = 0.5$ mA with measured currents $I_m = 0.5$ mA, 1 mA and $\sqrt{2}$ mA (RIRT_NIST, 33.6 s sampling). (b) Response for $I_c = 1$ mA with $I_m = 0.5$ mA, 1 mA and $\sqrt{2}$ mA. (c) Response for $I_c = \sqrt{2}$ mA with $I_m = 0.5$ mA, 1 mA and $\sqrt{2}$ mA. (d) Average temperature response (originates from Joule heating contribution ($P = I^2R$) in the sensing element). (e) Temperature instability response (arises from the combined effects of temperature resolution limit and current-induced self-heating).

(c) Microwave signal power determination

One key function of our CIGT is to *in-situ* measure thermodynamic temperature in the resonator using microwave techniques. While higher microwave signal power improves measurement resolution, it also induces stronger heating effects on the resonator, potentially destabilizing thermal control. Thus, power levels must be carefully balanced to minimize temperature perturbations.

For accurate identification of the critical power threshold, determination of microwave signal power was carried out at the lowest operating temperature (4 K) under vacuum, yielding maximal sensitivity to thermal perturbations. Figure 10(a) displays the thermal perturbation induced by varying microwave signal powers (P_{MV}) on the resonator maintained at ~ 4 K under vacuum, monitored using the RIRT_NIST. As the power increases from -30 dBm⁶ (1 μW) to -10 dBm (100 μW), the resonator temperature exhibits minimal fluctuation amplitude. However, beyond -7 dBm (200 μW), the fluctuation

amplitude begins to rise, particularly at -5 dBm (~ 316 μW). These results identify -10 dBm as the optimal operating power at 4 K, providing an optimal compromise between microwave signal resolution and temperature instability.

This observation is further supported by the frequency spectra derived from the FFT of the resonator temperature (figure 10(b)). A key advantage of this method is its capability for rapid detection of potential oscillations, significantly reducing the required observation time compared to conventional approaches. Distinct oscillations at approximately 0.0021 Hz are evident for microwave signal powers $P_{MV} = -5$ dBm and -7 dBm, corresponding to a period of ~ 480 s. This behavior correlates with the 480 s measurement cycle period of the six microwave modes (TM11, TE11, TM12, TE12, TM13, TE13) shown in figure 10(c), confirming the thermal response is synchronized with the mode interrogation sequence. The heating effect of the microwave modes on the resonator varies with mode type; higher-frequency modes generally induce greater energy loss and thus stronger heating. However, for $P_{MV} \leq -10$ dBm, these oscillations become negligible, prompting the selection of -10 dBm as the optimal signal power at 4 K. Theoretically, this optimal power should

⁶ dBm = $10 \times \log_{10}(P/\text{mW})$, where P denotes the microwave single power in milliwatts (mW).

Figure 10. Temperature control results of the resonator at 4 K under vacuum conditions with varying microwave signal powers, monitored via the RIRT_NIST with $\tau = 33.6 \text{ s}$. (a) Temperature perturbation induced by different microwave powers. (b) Frequency spectra obtained from FFT analysis of resonator temperature fluctuations. (c) Measurement cycle period for six microwave modes (TM11, TE11, TM12, TE12, TM13, TE13). (d) Comparative evolution of average resonator temperature and instability without and with microwave measurements across different signal powers.

scale with resonator temperature due to the increasing heat capacity. For simplicity, however, the experimentally determined optimal power (-10 dBm) was adopted throughout this study.

Figure 10(d) compares the evolution of the average resonator temperature and its instability under two operational conditions: with microwave measurements (across varying signal powers) and without microwave measurements. Power sweep tests show strong hysteresis-free repeatability: temperature instabilities not exceeding 2.2 μK and <2.5 μK offset in average temperature between increasing/decreasing power scans in the full cycles (-30 dBm \rightarrow -5 dBm \rightarrow -30 dBm). As the signal power increases, both the average resonator temperature and its instability exhibit a marked increase, with a distinct transition observed at -10 dBm. Notably, all measured temperature shifts remain within their respective instability limits when compared to the no-microwave baseline. At the optimal power of -10 dBm, the average microwave-induced heating effect is limited to less than 3 μK . This thermal perturbation would decrease further at higher temperatures due to increasing heat capacity of the resonator.

3.2.2. Temperature control instability. Based on these parameter optimizations, we implemented long-term temperature stabilization from 4 K to 25 K under various microwave measurement conditions.

(a) Long-term temperature control

Figure 11 shows 12 h instability performance under vacuum at 4 K, 5 K, 13.8 K and 24.6 K, monitored using the standard thermometer RIRT_NIST with 1 mA excitation current ($\tau = 33$ s). The achieved temperature stabilities are 6.1 $\mu\text{K}@4$ K, 6.7 $\mu\text{K}@5$ K, 7.8 $\mu\text{K}@13.8$ K and 7.4 $\mu\text{K}@24.6$ K. All these measured stabilities (better than 8 μK) significantly surpass our 15 μK instability requirement for the resonator in CITC.

(b) Overall temperature control performance

Figure 12 presents the temperature instability performance of the copper block and resonator across the 4 K– 25 K range during multiple CITC runs. Using the developed control methods, we achieved stabilization within 10 μK (1σ) of the target temperatures (figure 12(a)), exceeding the 15 μK requirement by 33% . The corresponding relative temperature stabilities are better than 2 ppm (figure 12(b)), less than one-fifth of typical relative uncertainty (>10 ppm) of thermodynamic temperature in this range. These results demonstrate the exceptional precision of CITC in cryogenic thermal control.

In future, temperature instability could be further improved by several ways, including using ultra-low-noise instruments,

Figure 11. Long-term temperature instability of the resonator at low temperatures with microwave measurements ($P_{\text{MV}} = -10$ dBm) under vacuum conditions, monitored using RIRT_NIST ($\tau = 33.6$ s).

upgraded 100 Ω standard resistance thermometers (replacing 50 Ω standards), adopting lower-resistance electrical connections and further developing more robust control algorithms.

3.3. Multibrige measurement

Using the stabilized cryogenic platform, multibrige measurements for comparison or calibration were investigated via four bridges (one AC bridge F900 and three superthermometers 1594A) and eleven thermometers. The F900 was used to measure the reference thermometer RIRT_NIST, while the three 1594A bridges were employed to monitor (PtCo_X1, PtCo_X3, PtCo_X6, PtCo_X9), (PtCo_X2, PtCo_X4, PtCo_X7) and (RIRT_NPL3, PtCo_X5, PtCo_X8) respectively, as listed in table 1.

Figure 13 presents self-heating measurements of eleven thermometers at 5 K using our multibrige method, demonstrating a 4-fold speed improvement (3 h) compared to single F900 bridges (12 h) and 2-fold improvement over 1594A bridges (6 h). The developed method enables simultaneous calibration of multiple thermometers, demonstrating excellent consistency in both zero-current resistance (R_0) and self-heating coefficients (R_{SH}) between single-bridge and multibrige methods. As shown in figure 14, the observed deviations (ΔR_0 , ΔR_{SH}) fall within experimental uncertainties. Furthermore, the approach reduces measurement uncertainties in both R_0 and R_{SH} by up to 33% compared to conventional methods (figure 15). These results validate the proposed technique as an efficient, high-throughput solution for precision thermometer calibration and comparison over the temperature range under investigation.

Figure 12. Temperature instability of the copper block (5 K–25 K) and resonator (4 K–25 K) across multiple experimental runs. (a) Absolute instability $\sigma(T)$; (b) Relative instability $\sigma_r(T)$. Copper block: monitored via RIRT_INRiM (1 mA excitation, $\tau = 33.6$ s) in Runs 6–8 (vacuum, no microwave). Resonator: measured using RIRT_INRiM (Run 9) or RIRT_NIST (Runs 10–18) with 1 mA excitation ($\tau = 33.6$ s) and -10 dBm microwave power.

Figure 13. Experimental demonstration of the proposed multibrige comparison and calibration method in self-heating measurements of 11 thermometers by using one Wika F900 AC bridge and three super-thermometers 1494A. The two currents are $i_1 = 1$ mA and $i_2 = \sqrt{2}$ mA. In self-heating measurement, $t_0 = 20$ min for F900 bridge and $t_0 = 10$ min for super-thermometers.

4. Conclusion and perspectives

Facing the implementation and dissemination of the new kelvin, especially the requirement for a direct comparison of T in future in a wide range, we designed and constructed an ultra-stable CITC at TIPC-CAS to provide an μK -level instability (relative instability at the ppm level) working environment from 4 K to 25 K, and proposed multibrige comparison and calibration methods to realize measurements in a more precise and efficient way.

The developed CITC system achieves stable cryogenic cooling to 3.9 K within 30 h while maintaining exceptional

temperature instability (0.6 mK) on both the pressure vessel and resonator through an innovative passive control design. The system combines multi-stage radiation shielding to minimize environmental thermal noise with optimized thermal links that simultaneously enhance cooling power transfer from the secondary cold head and suppress temperature fluctuations. This dual approach reduces temperature variations by two orders of magnitude, from 243 mK (peak-to-peak) to just 1.8 mK, demonstrating the effectiveness of passive control for precision cryogenic applications.

Besides, we developed a three-level cascade active temperature regulation system with a ‘dynamic

Figure 14. Self-heating and resistance differences between conventional single-bridge and the proposed multibrIDGE methods for the ten thermometers. (a) $\Delta R_0 = R_0, \text{multibrIDGE} - R_0, \text{single-bridge}$; (b) $\Delta R_{SH} = R_{SH}, \text{multibrIDGE} - R_{SH}, \text{single-bridge}$. Error bars: uncertainty of $R_0, \text{multibrIDGE}$ and $R_{SH}, \text{multibrIDGE}$.

Figure 15. Improvement in uncertainty in percent for both self-heating and zero-current resistance measurements for the ten thermometers by using the proposed multibrIDGE method.

compensation—rough stabilization—precision regulation’ strategy. The system combines source-side heat compensation on 2nd cold head, mid-path coarse PID control on the 2nd flange, and final-stage precision PID regulation on pressure vessel. Based on synergistic passive and active regulation strategies, the CITC achieved excellent temperature instability of 8 μK (2 ppm relative) at temperatures from 4 K to 25 K, potentially for metrological applications. The typical standard deviations are 6.1 μK (4 K), 6.7 μK (5 K), 7.8 μK (13.8 K), and 7.4 μK (24.6 K) at 33.6 s integration time, approaching the measurement limits of our AC bridge and reference thermometers. These performances could be further improved by using higher sensitivity sensors in future.

Furthermore, our experiments confirm the feasibility of the multibrIDGE comparison and calibration methods by using one AC bridge and three super-thermometers at 5 K. Measurements can be performed at least twice as fast while improving precision, reducing uncertainties in self-heating and zero-current resistance by up to 33%. These advances make it possible to realize rapid, high-throughput, and high-precision comparison and calibration of multiple thermometers across various temperature points.

The results demonstrate that both the CITC technique and our multibrIDGE method enhance measurement accuracy and

reliability, thereby strengthening confidence in their application for high-accuracy thermometer calibration and international thermodynamic temperature comparisons across the 4 K–25 K range, as currently implemented under the DireK-T project.

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